

A fast half-subtractor using 8T static random access memory for in-memory computation

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 28, 2024

Revised Oct 22, 2024

Accepted Nov 12, 2024

Keywords:

Computation-in memory

Half subtractor

Latch-based sense amplifier

Static noise margin

Von-neumann

ABSTRACT

The existing system for computation completely incorporates Von-Neumann architecture which has limitations with respect to its memory, parallelism and power constraints. This has affected the efficiency of the computing system. Novel architectural solutions are required to meet the growing demands for improved computational efficiency and power management in very large scale integration (VLSI) systems. To deal with the large-scale data, computation in memory (CIM) has been introduced. The paper presents the half subtractor circuit and the In-memory computation co-design using eight transistors static random access memory (SRAM) cell whose read circuitry is transmission gate based. The proposed half-subtractor with the CIM is implementation is carried out in 180 nm complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) technology. The sensing scheme used is the latch-based sense amplifier along with the 8T SRAM cell. The proposed SRAM with transmission-gate based read circuitry along with latch-based sense amplifier reduces the delay and power consumed during the read operation significantly and a bit reduction during the write operation. The static noise margin (SNM) for read operation has been increased by 9% in the transmission gate-based SRAM as compared to conventional 8T SRAM. The delay of the proposed design has been reduced by 53% during the read operation and 4.43% during the write operation. The power consumed has been reduced by 3% and 8.6% during read and write operations, respectively.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Von-Neumann architecture based computing systems which are being used at present [1] has the arithmetic and logic unit (ALU) unit and the memory unit placed far from each other leading to high power consumption during the transfer of data from memory unit to the ALU unit and this can be shown in the Figure 1. To overcome the Von-Neumann bottleneck, computation in memory (CIM) has been introduced. This system has ALU and memory unit nearby and the power consumed will be reduced [2]-[4]. The computation in-memory architecture is shown in the Figure 2. This structure will conserve energy used during the transfer of data. Numerous papers could be observed in the literature, that centers its observation on complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) based static random access memory (SRAM) for CIM

technology. 6T SRAMs have been used to implement the CIM methodology [5]. But the 6T SRAM has the disadvantage of read distribution failure [6]. To overcome the read disturbance failure, 8T SRAM cells have been used effectively [7]. Boolean functions such as NOR and NAND are implemented and shown [8], [9]. Similarly, using these approaches, a fast adder has been implemented where the number of logic gates has been reduced to reduce the delay of the circuit [10].

Figure 1. Von-Neumann architecture

Figure 2. CIM architecture

The different sensing schemes have been proposed but the latch-based sense amplifier has proven to be the best one for the detection of small changes in the bit line of 8T SRAM [11]. 8T SRAMs were also used in computation of dot product [12]. Some of the works also discussed on the spin-transfer torque magnetic RAM and its computation architecture [13]. Prospects of this new emerging technology has been discussed in few papers [14]. Even though the noise margin of 6T SRAM cells were better, 8T SRAMs were considered because of the presence of separate paths for read and write [15].

The contributions made by this proposed work primarily are a fast subtractor has been implemented with the SRAM array for in memory computation which results in reduction in the delay as well as power consumed after the usage of transmission based read circuitry in the 8T SRAM cell. The paper is organized as: section 2 consists of 8T SRAM which are conventional and transistor based. The section 3 contains the mapping of half subtractor NOR circuit into the SRAM array and its implementation. The section 4 discusses the results and analysis while the section 5 contains conclusion and future scope.

2. METHOD

The complete method is divided into two sections. Section 2.1 details the implementation of 8T SRAM and shows the read and write path along with the sense amplifier design. Section 2.2 explains the implementation 2×5 SRAM memory array equipped with a half subtractor. NOR netlist used for the half-subtractor, which consists of five NOR gates and subtracts two 1-bit binary numbers (A, B) and provides output as two 1-bit binary numbers (difference and borrow). The conventional design used pass transistors for the read circuitry [8]. The read circuitry has been replaced with transmission gate in the proposed work. The half subtractor is realized using NOR gates and those gates were mapped into the SRAM array to get the arithmetic circuit and CIM cell co-design. Then the simulation was carried out to compare the obtained results with the conventional design. The circuit implementation for functionality, delay and power analysis is done using the CADENCE virtuoso tool in 180 nm CMOS technology.

2.1. 8T static random access memory

The complete storing of data as well as processing of data will be done in the memory array itself. There are two-word lines and two-bit lines for 8T SRAM cell and this is the reason for choosing 8T SRAM over 6T SRAM cell. The conventional 8T SRAM cell is shown in the Figure 3. Choosing 8T SRAM will eliminate the read disturbance failure. 6T SRAM will be present in the 8T SRAM cell and two additional transistors are present for the read operation. The write operation performed in the 8T SRAM cell is similar to that of the 6T SRAM cell.

Figure 3. Conventional 8T SRAM cell

The write word line is made high and the V_{DD} must be given to word bit line and word bit line bar must be provided with ground. This will store 1 at Q and 0 at Qbar of the SRAM memory unit. Bit 0 can be written in the same way by reversing the terminals. Bit line will be recharged before the commencement of read operation. The transistors which are present in the read circuitry will be used during the read operation [3], [16]-[24].

The read word line must be ON to be able to get the value at the read bit line output. Now if the read circuitry is replaced by a transmission gate, then it reduces the total area occupancy along with the significant delay reduction during the read operation. When the word line of the read circuitry is ON, only then the transmission gate is activated resulting in the reduction of power and delay produced by the circuit. The Figure 4 shows the design of the 8T SRAM cell whose read circuitry is replaced by transmission gate. To detect even the smallest difference in the bit line voltage read from the SRAM, sense amplifiers are used. On comparing the results and speed of the sense amplifiers, latch-based sense amplifier is best suited for the proposed design [25]. There is a positive feedback present in the sense amplifier which is latch based. Due to the presence of positive feedback in latch-based sense amplifiers, they are very fast. The latch-based sense amplifier design is shown in the Figure 5.

Figure 4. 8T SRAM with transmission gate-based read circuitry

Figure 5. Latch-based sense amplifier

The INN input in the sense amplifier must be connected to the reference voltage (V_{ref}) which must be at its maximum that is V_{DD} when the input given is (11), V_{ref} should be half of V_{DD} if the input combination given as (01) or (10). If the input is (00), the V_{ref} should be minimum. The INP terminal mentioned in the Latch-based sense amplifier is connected to the bit line (RQ) of the SRAM shown in the Figure 2. The output is taken out from the terminal SO and SON terminal gives the compliment of the SO output. Five such sense amplifiers are used.

2.2. Circuit implementation

In this case, a 2×5 SRAM memory array is equipped with a half subtractor. Figure 6 display the NOR netlist for the half-subtractor, which consists of five NOR gates and subtracts two 1-bit binary numbers (A, B) and provides output as two 1-bit binary numbers (difference and borrow). Utilizing the following equation, the output was created from the input. Difference= AB' and borrow= $A' \cdot B$.

Figure 6. Half-subtractor realization using NOR gates

The half-subtractor can be realized using NOR gates only as shown in the Figure 6. The half-subtractor netlist will be mapped into the SRAM array to perform the arithmetic circuit and memory cell co-design. In an 8T SRAM cell, there is 6T SRAM cell and an extra read port consisting of transistors P3 and N5 as in Figure 4. The write operation is similar to the 6T SRAM cell but the read operation is different. When the read operation has to occur, RL must be kept high while keeping the WWL low. Cells A and B from the Figure 7 represents 6T SRAM cell part and the extra transmission gate-based read circuitry is connected to have read operation and the output of the bits read from it will be reflected on the RBL line. When both the inputs were given as logic '0'. Cells A and B stored '0' in their memory unit. During the operation, RBL is precharged to V_{DD} . Since both the inputs are '0', the RBL will have no change and retains the V_{DD} voltage which is sense by the sense amplifier and the output was observed to be 1. If anyone of the Cells contents were changed from '0' to '1', the RBL starts discharging and the output observed at the sense amplifier was '0'. Hence, it can be inferred that as a result, NOR can be implemented in the 8T bit-cell with minimal overhead if both of the read word lines are activated simultaneously.

Figure 7. Single-ended sensing of NOR

Using the designs and approach shown in Figures 6 and 7, complete circuit was implemented as shown in the Figure 8. The two bits A and B gets stored in the cells. RBL lines are precharged to V_{DD} through the precharge transistors. Each of the NOR gates are mapped into the two row, 5 Column SRAM array. Since serial mapping of each NOR gate into a separate column has been done and each NOR gate has a different delay, the precharge circuit was controlled to produce the desired half subtractor result. Since each NOR gate has a different delay, the RBL of the subsequent column precharges when the input from the previous column becomes available. Then, to obtain the half-subtractor result for all input combinations, simulation of the NOR netlist mapped SRAM array was carried out in Cadence virtuoso tool using 180 nm CMOS technology.

Figure 8. Mapping half-subtractor circuit into SRAM array

To obtain the half-subtractor result for all input combinations, simulation of the NOR netlist mapped SRAM array was carried out in Cadence virtuoso tool using 180 nm CMOS technology. The output of the sense amplifiers 2 and 5 gives out the required outputs of half subtractor, borrow, and difference, respectively. The integration of half subtractor and SRAM array optimizes the overall performance, making the CIM subtractor well-suited for high-speed, low-power computational tasks.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The CIM design is implemented in CADENCE by using all the above designs. The schematic diagram in cadence 180 nm technology is as shown in the Figure 9. The circuit is simulated to obtain the transient response giving the simulation time as 2 us. The response obtained is the waveform of a half subtractor circuit. Whenever the enable signal is high, outputs borrow and difference are inspected. EN=1, input A=1, B=1, output difference=0; borrow=0; input A=1, B=0, output difference=1; input A=0, B=0, output difference=0; borrow=0; input A=0, B=1, output difference=1; borrow=0; and the functionality is verified. The waveform after simulation is as shown in the Figure 10.

Figure 9. CIM cell implemented in 180 nm CMOS technology

Figure 10. Simulated response of the proposed work

From the response, it can be observed that the half subtractor output waveform was achieved. A and B represents the inputs stored in SRAM cells A and B. The corresponding difference and borrow outputs were shown. There exists some delay during both the read and write operation. The conventional 8T SRAM CIM design as proposed in the paper [7] shows that the read delay, power and energy consumed by it are found to be 9.756 ps, 417.4 nW, and 4.069 zj, respectively. The same as computed with the proposed

methodology gives out the results as 4.605 ps, 406.5 nW, and 1.871 zj. The readings are tabulated in the Tables 1 and 2. Similarly, if we consider the write operation, the write delay, power and energy consumed by it are found to be 62.85 ps, 1.579 nW, and 0.099 zj when it comes to existing design [7]. The proposed design gives out the write delay, power and energy consumed as 60.07 ps, 1.459 nW, and 0.088 zj. On comparison, the proposed design had a noticeable reduction in the read operation rather than write operation. This is mainly due to the usage of transmission gate based read circuitry in the 8T SRAM design.

Table 1. Power, delay, and energy details of read operation

Design	Read delay (ps)	Read power (nW)	Read energy (zj)
Existing design with conventional 8T SRAM [7]	9.756	417.4	4.069
Proposed design with SRAM using transmission gate based read circuitry	4.605	406.5	1.871

Table 2. Power, delay, and energy details of write operation

Design	Write delay (ps)	Write power (nW)	Write energy (zj)
Existing design with conventional 8T SRAM [7]	62.85	1.579	0.099
Proposed design with SRAM using transmission gate based read circuitry	60.7	1.459	0.088

Additionally, static noise margin (SNM) of the transmission gate-based SRAM cell has 209.585 mv whereas the conventional SRAM has the SNM as 192.79 mv. That means 9% increase in the noise margin. Greater the noise margin, better will be the design. Hence the half subtractor was implemented and it can be used in the computing system as ALU and memory array both, so it has wider application in the computing system. The transmission gate based read circuitry incorporated with the CIM will significantly reduce the delay. Optimizing the power and delay improves overall efficiency, allowing the system to perform more effectively while consuming less energy. These factors together enhance the design's performance, making it faster and more efficient.

4. CONCLUSION

In the field of very large scale integration (VLSI) design, power, and delay optimization are fundamental challenges that drive both innovation and practical implementations, especially in the development of energy-efficient and compact devices. The choice of state of art transmission gate based read circuitry for 8T SRAM cell has enhanced the performance in of computation in-memory in terms of both area and delay. It was discovered that the latch-based sense amplifiers worked well for detecting and amplifying the little variations in the bit line signal. The finest sense amplifiers in terms of speed turned out to be latch-based. It makes the amplifier faster since it has significant positive feedback. The complete half-subtractor functionality has been realized using NOR gates completely and those are mapped using the SRAM array to get its functionality for in-memory computation. This design has been implemented using Cadence Virtuoso in 180 nm technology. It has been observed that the delay produced by the proposed work is reduced by 53% when compared to conventional design during read operation. Similarly, the delay has been reduced by 4.4% during write operation. The power consumed by the circuit has also been reduced by 3% and 8.6% during read and write operation. Further the design can be extended to other higher circuits such as multipliers, dividers, and other combinational circuits which can be realized using CIM and ultimately, the complete Von-Neumann architecture can be replaced by the in-memory computation architecture.

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